

RE-DWELL Workshop 2 (Budapest)

Deliverable 3.2

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 3.2 RE-DWELL Workshop 2 (Budapest)

Version 1

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Executive summary

Three international workshops have been planned to take place in Lisbon (2021), Budapest (2022), and Zagreb (2023) as part of the RE-DWELL project. The second of these workshops, organized by the Centre for Social Sciences (CSS) has been carried out during the second year of the project activities in Budapest, from March 28 to 30, 2022.

The theme of the Budapest workshop, "Community Involvement in Affordable and Sustainable Housing," was approached from a sociological perspective, focusing on socio-spatial inequalities, financialization and housing, and green homes and communities. The workshop programme fulfilled various objectives: to follow up on the development of the ESRs' research by fostering networking between the individual research projects, to conduct training activities related to two structured courses (RMT2 and TS2), to continue with the collaborative research work (vocabulary and case studies library) and to engage local stakeholders in the networking actions (non-academic sectors, local administrations and civic organizations concerned with sustainable and affordable housing).

The first session of the RMT2 course "RMT2 Course: Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis" took place on the first day of the workshop. A hands-on session enabled students to discuss the various perspectives on housing comparative research in groups. Likewise, the first session of the TS2 Course "Entrepreneurship; professional and career development" took place on the last day. It addressed the concepts of and approaches to entrepreneurship, highlighting entrepreneurial opportunities, ventures, and types of activity and indicators. Finally, the ongoing work on the vocabulary and case study library was presented and reviewed.

An open roundtable was held on the topic of "Community Engagement", with the online participation of Prof. Jenny Pickerill and Prof. Richard Lang, and moderated on-site by Prof. Gerard van Bortel.

Local NGOs and secondment representatives were involved in the organization and implementation of some workshop activities, including:

- Projection and discussion of the documentary "No Country for the Poor", with the participation of two members of the organisation AVM, A Város Mindenkié (The City for All).
- Urban rehabilitation in District VIII, lectures and site visit organized by the local Urban Rehabilitation and Development Company (RÉV8) and the partner organisation MRI.
- A serious game facilitated by the local NGO CoHousing Budapest Association.

Posters of ongoing ESRs' projects were on display during the event. The poster exhibition prompted a discussion on the most appropriate way to represent research projects in this format.

The work carried out at the Budapest workshop represented a step forward for network members as it helped them to understand the challenges of affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The experience gained in this workshop also contributed to creating a collaborative and transdisciplinary research environment in which early-stage researchers (ESRs) can work side by side with each other to develop their projects.

1. Introduction

The second workshop was held between 27 and 30 March 2022 at the Centre for Social Sciences in Budapest. The aim of the workshop was to foster the knowledge exchange between ESRs, supervisors and non-academic organisations on the challenges and opportunities on “Community participation in affordable and sustainable housing”. The programme included sessions dedicated to addressing the topic of the workshop from multiple perspectives. The participants included guest speakers from professional practice and academia.

Throughout the different activities of the programme, ESRs had the opportunity to demonstrate their ability to present and communicate research ideas and outputs to expert and non-expert audiences, improve their understanding of transdisciplinary research methodologies and their application to their own projects, develop personal skills and self-management competences, and engage with local stakeholders.

This report summarizes the work done during the workshop. It encompasses the programme of activities, the work done by ESRs before the workshop, the RTM2 and TS2 courses in-person activities, and the workshop evaluation by ESRs, supervisors and co-supervisors.

The report is also useful for faculty members from other institutions to learn about the work done in RE-DWELL, the aim of which is to increase the knowledge and understanding on the compatibility between affordable and sustainable housing across Europe through a holistic and transdisciplinary research and training programme.

1.1. Contribution of local partners

CSS was in charge of the organization of the workshop. The collaboration of local organizations from the non-academic sectors became key to accomplishing the learning objectives and strengthening the ties with local stakeholders. “The City for All” group participated in the discussion about a documentary about homelessness and RÉV8 – Magdolna Quarter, Budapest District VIII– gave a presentation and a tour of the social projects in the neighbourhood, together with József Hegedüs, from the Metropolitan Research Institute (MRI), a RE-DWELL partner organisation,

1.2. Participants

There were 29 participants (2 online), including ESRs, supervisors/co-supervisors, guest speakers and external partners (Figure 1). 15 ESRs (14 in-person, and 1 online), 13 supervisors/co-supervisors (12 in-person, 1 online), and 1 local partner organisation (in-person) participated in the workshop, namely (in-person unless indicated):

- B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain. Leandro Madrazo, project coordinator; Annette Davis, Saskia Furman (ESRs)
- B2 University Grenoble Alpes, France. Jean-Christophe Verrier (co-supervisor); Christophe Verrier (ESR)
- B3 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom. Karim Hadjri (supervisor), Krzysztof Nawratek (co-supervisor); Aya Elghandour, Mahmoud Alsaeed (ESRs)
- B4 University of Zagreb, Croatia. Gojko Bezovan (supervisor); Marko Horvat (ESR)

- B5 CSS Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence, Hungary. Gábor Csanádi (co-supervisor) Adrienne Csizmady (supervisor); Anna Martin (ESR)
- B6 University of Cyprus, Cyprus. Nadia Charalambous (supervisor), Andreas Savvides (co-supervisor); Effrosyni Roussou, Andreas Panagidis (online) (ESRs)
- B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain. Carla Sentieri (supervisor); Zoe Tzika (ESR)
- B8 TU Delft, Netherlands. Gerard van Bortel (co-supervisor), Marietta Haffner (supervisor) (online); Tijn Croon, Alex Fernández (ESRs)
- B9 ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal. Alexandra Paio (supervisor); Androniki Pappa, Carlolina Martín (ESRs)
- B10 University of Reading, United Kingdom. Leonardo Ricaurte (ESR)
- PO12 Metropolitan Research Institute. József Hegedüs (co-supervisor)

Figure 1. RE-DWELL participants in the Budapest workshop

1.3. RTM and TS training activities

The first sessions of the RMT2 and TS2 courses took place during the workshop. The two courses were designed to be implemented in a blended mode (Figures 2, 3), with face-to-face sessions in the Budapest workshop and the Valencia summer school, and online sessions in between both events.

RMT2 session

The first session of the RMT2 course was dedicated to presenting the overall programme of the course, and to introducing the basic notions of comparative research in the field of housing, history and methods. After the lectures, students discussed the literature they had been requested to read in small groups before attending the workshop.

TS2 session

TS2 first session consisted of a combination of mini-lectures and a workshop to introduce the ESRs to entrepreneurship and enterprise covering knowledge exchange, commercialisation and social enterprise. The session also discussed entrepreneurship concepts and approaches, highlighting entrepreneurial opportunities, ventures, activity types and indicators. The workshop focused on how enterprising a researcher can be using the Research Development Framework self-perfection questionnaire.

Research Methods and Tools 2 (RMT2)

Figure 2. RMT2 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
From: Gerard van Bortel (TUD),

Figure 3. TS2 course structure as integrated with the network activities.
 From: Karim Hadjri (USFD), Transferable Skills 2 (TS2)

1.4. Dissemination

There were dissemination activities before and during the event, on different media (website, social media, emails), and for diverse target groups: researchers, local associations, professors, PhD students, policymakers and the general public. The event was disseminated on the RE-DWELL website and its social media channels (Figure 4) before and during the activities of the workshop (Instagram, Twitter and Facebook) (Figures 5 and 6). A CSS photographer made a photo report on the three-day programme. After the workshop, ESRs published some reflections about their experiences in the RE-DWELL [blog](#). The video of the [roundtable](#) was uploaded to the RE-DWELL YouTube channel (Figure 7). These dissemination activities are also included in Deliverable 5.10 “Dissemination and Communication Outreach”.

RE-DWELL Workshop #2 Budapest
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The Budapest workshop aims to foster knowledge exchange between ESRs, supervisors and non-academic organisations on the challenges and opportunities about "Community participation in affordable and sustainable housing".

Invited speakers from professional practice, academia and local administrations will address the workshop topic from multiple perspectives. The lectures will be followed by panel discussions and complemented by site visits. A roundtable with guest speakers will be open to the public via an online session.

In addition, the programme of activities will facilitate the further development of ESRs skills through training activities that are part of the structured courses (RMT2 and T52).

Figure 4. Dissemination on RE-DWELL website

Figure 5. Dissemination during the workshop on RE-DWELL's Facebook page

Figure 6. Dissemination during the workshop on Twitter

Figure 7. Recording of the RE-DWELL Roundtable #3 (available on RE-DWELL's YouTube Channel)

During the workshop, there was an exhibition of the posters created by ESRs to present their research project at CSS (Figure 8). The exhibition enabled participants to have an open discussion about the ESRs' projects and about the ways to represent them in a poster. The posters are included in Annex 1.

Figure 8. Poster exhibition of ESR projects at CSS

2. Programme

The programme was available in the [project website](#) before the start of the workshop. It was an on-site event, with the possibility of joining online. It started with a guided tour on Sunday, 27 March and ended on Wednesday, 30 March (Table 1).

Table 1. Programme of the workshop

Day	Timetable	Activities
DAY 0 Sunday, 27 March, 2022	17:00 to 18:00	Guided Tour
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 1 Monday, 28 March, 2022	09:30 to 10:00	Welcome
	10:00 to 12:30	Presentation of ESRs' research projects
	12:30 to 13:00	ESRs' research plan diagrams exhibition
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch
	14:00 to 17:00	Roundtable discussion
	17:00 to 19:00	Documentary and discussion
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 2 Tuesday, 29 March, 2022	09:30 to 13:00	RMT2 course
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch
	14:00 to 15:45	Vocabulary
	16:00 to 18:00	Case study Budapest
	18:00 to 19:00	Site visit to the case study area
	20:00	Dinner
DAY 3 Wednesday, 30 March, 2021	09:30 to 12:30	TS2 course
	12:30 to 13:00	ESR research plan diagrams exhibition
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch
	14:00 to 15:45	Case study library
	16:00 to 17:00	Network communication processes
	17:00 to 18:00	Meeting ESRs and management board
	18 :00 to 19:00	Game time
	20:00	Dinner

2.1. Activities

DAY 0

Sunday, 27 March

Guided Tour

A tour of the inner city district of Budapest (District VII, Elizabeth Town) focused on affordable and sustainable housing in a neighbourhood currently experiencing gentrification. It was guided by Gergely Olt (CSS research fellow) and it provided an opportunity for participants to start to interact with each other in an informal setting (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Guided tour to District VII

Dinner

The participants were invited to dinner at Twentysix Budapest, a courtyard and building transformed into a restaurant and hub, resembling a botanical garden in the heart of downtown Budapest (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Dinner at Twentysix Budapest

DAY 1

Monday, 28 March

The first day of the programme included the opening session, an update of the ongoing research projects in the form of presentations and poster exhibitions, a roundtable with two guest speakers to discuss community participation in affordable and sustainable housing and the projection of the documentary “No Country for the Poor”, followed by a discussion.

Welcome

The workshop started with the welcome words of the director of the Institute of Sociology, Adrienne Csizmady (CSS), and the RE-DWELL project coordinator, Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL).

Presentation of ESRs research projects

Adrienne Csizmady moderated the session in which the ESRs presented a summary of their ongoing research, including the research background, literature review, methodology and secondments (Figure 11). During the session, ESRs created links between their projects and the other projects using a table setup on Miro (see Annex 2).

Figure 11. Presentations of ESRs research projects

ESR research plan diagrams exhibition

Before the workshop, ESRs submitted the posters of summarizing the status of the research projects (see Annex 1). The posters were displayed in the lobby of the Centre for Social Sciences (Figure 12). The information provided by the posters complemented the previous presentations in the room. ESRs were able to judge themselves which posters communicated more effectively the research project. There was a discussion about the skills that are needed to do a poster, and the need to have a specific training.

Figure 12. Exhibition of posters of the ESR projects at the workshop premises

Roundtable discussion “Community participation”

After a lunch in the Centre for Social Sciences, the roundtable on community participation took place in a hybrid format (Figure 13). It was moderated by Gerard van Bortel (TUD) and the guest speakers were:

- Jenny Pickerill, Professor of Environmental Geography and Head of Department of Geography at Sheffield University, England
- Richard Lang, Full Professor of Social Enterprise and Innovative Regions at Bertha von Suttner Private University in St. Pölten, Austria.

Figure 13. ESRs present in Budapest addressing questions to the panellists

Firstly, the guest speakers tackled the question of how community participation can be embedded into research. Richard Lang introduced a project they are working on the potential of collaborative modules to support refugee integration using the methodological framework of “transition management”. Jenny Pickerill’s research focused mostly on community-led grassroots experiments. Community participation becomes relevant in this case as Pickerill relies on “activist participatory research methodology”. ESRs could further understand the complexity of the roundtable topic by asking questions and sharing insights.

A recording of the roundtable is available in the project [website](#). An account of the roundtable can be found in a blog post by Zoe Tzika (ESR10) “Community participation in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing | discussing inclusion/exclusion” on the [website](#).

Documentary and discussion

The last session of the first day was dedicated to the projection and discussion of the documentary “No Country for the Poor” which deals with the housing crisis in Hungary (Figure 14). Two members of AVM, A Város Mindenkié (The City for All) attended the session and answered the questions of the audience (Figure 15). Lea Kőszeghy (CSS) moderated the session.

"In Hungary, the poor and weak are increasingly stigmatized to obscure the failure of the state. Today 120,000 state-owned flats stand empty, while almost 30,000 people have no home. AVM, A Város Mindenkié (The City for All) is a group of homeless people and activists that confronts the authorities to defend the right to shelter, social welfare and human dignity. They work to improve the situation of people in poverty by speaking up against unjust social policies. The group protests by occupying Parliament Square, preventing evictions, lobbying local authorities and providing pro bono legal aid to those in need. AVM is a mini-society based on solidarity and democracy in a society that is gradually drifting "the other way". Three years of intensive research into AVM's life has given us unprecedented access to the group and its protagonists. Their community and their shared sense of purpose give them the strength to fight injustices, in line with the Civil Rights Movement tradition. Their personal stories and reflections inspire agency and citizenship that means taking life into your own hands. Many ask, what is democracy in Europe today? What is its face in a country like Hungary, where every third citizen lives under the poverty line, where social housing makes up less than 3% of the housing stock?"

Figure 14. "No Country for the Poor"
(poster and synopsis from IMDB)

Figure 15. Invited guests from A Város Mindenkié

DAY 2

Tuesday, 29 March

The first session of the RMT2 course, which took place on the second day of the Budapest workshop, was dedicated to a peer-to-peer review of the entries submitted, a review of the shared vocabulary, and a visit to District VIII.

RMT2 Course: Comparative methodologies based on quantitative and qualitative data analysis

The RMT2 course started with a presentation of the objectives, structure, planning, activities, and various individual and group tasks for the ESRs, as well as the corresponding expected outcomes of their work. After an introductory lecture by Gerard van Bortel (TUD), the ESRs worked in small groups and reflected on the added value of the key literature in the field of comparative housing research methodologies and tools on their individual research.

Marietta Haffner (TUD) joined the meeting online and presented an overview of comparative housing research concepts and research strategies used in practice with the aim to better understand and reflect on some ins and outs in terms of comparability. She also provided a history of comparative housing research as part of the presentation.

After the presentation, the early stage researchers discussed various perspectives of comparative housing research in small groups. Then, they shared the outcomes of their dialog in a concluding plenary session.

Three main perspectives on comparative research were discussed. Using work from Kemeny (1998) and Aalbers (2022), ESRs discussed the possible convergence or divergence of housing systems, and rational and comparative perspectives. Other ESRs discussed examples of cross-border housing research, using work from Elsinga (2011) and Ronald (2011). Another group focussed on the possibility of knowledge transfer across cases in transdisciplinary research using the work of Adler et al. (2018).

Vocabulary

Leandro Madrazo (La Salle-URL) gave an overview of the structure of the vocabulary and explained the editorial processes which will be applied for publishing the entries currently being written by ESRs. The goal is that each ESR has one entry published on the website before the next meeting in Valencia.

After the presentation, a practical session followed. In this session ESRs working in groups discussed the relationships between concepts and make groups with the terms on a Miro board (Figure 16). The work that started in this session was completed after the workshop. Then, each ESR produced his/her own concept map relating the different concepts (see Annex 3).

Figure 16. Individual research projects exchange and draw mind maps drawn during the discussion

Case study Budapest: Community participation in affordable and sustainable housing

Anna Kerékgyártó (RÉV 8) and József Hegedűs (MRI) invited the participants to discuss the possibilities of introducing a housing cooperative model in Budapest, as well as community participation in District VIII of Budapest (Figure 17). The session was held at the headquarters of H13 which is an integrated community and service centre¹. Their main goal is to provide space for cultural and leisure activities for local residents and those providing cultural services in the district.

Figure 17. Presentation at the H13 by the external participant, József Hegedűs

Site visit to the case study area

After the presentation at H13, the participants took a guided walking tour in District VIII. The RÉV8 CEO Csilla Sárkány and staff member Anna Kerékgyártó presented the site of social rehabilitation, paying particular attention to the methods of community engagement and their achievements (Figure 18).

¹ Learn more about H13's activities at <https://www.h13.hu>

Figure 18. Walking tour in District VIII led by Csilla Sárkány and Anna Kerékyártó (RÉV 8)

DAY 3

Wednesday, 30 March

The closing day of the Budapest workshop included the starting session of the TS2 course, a discussion on case studies and another discussion on the network communication processes. Finally, future steps were discussed and as a concluding session ESRs participated in a game to gain experience about non-formal educational methods.

TS2 Course: Entrepreneurship; professional and career development

Session 1 of TS2 session introduced ESRs to entrepreneurship and enterprise, covering knowledge sharing, marketing and social enterprise. It addressed entrepreneurship concepts and approaches, highlighting entrepreneurial opportunities, ventures, and types of activity and indicators. The RDF Enterprise lens was used to highlight “the key knowledge, behaviours and attributes typically developed by researchers that can be acquired through, or used in, enterprise activities”, and also to guide the generation of ideas. RDF knowledge exchange lens was also used to provide an overview of the key knowledge, behaviours and attributes. Some emphasis was also given to social enterprise citing interesting case studies. The part focusing on Entrepreneurship opportunities and ventures covered IP rights, and referred to important cases, and also included some guidance on entrepreneurial activity which the ESRs found very stimulating.

The workshop focused on how to undertake research using the Research Development Framework self-perfection questionnaire. The main question was ‘How enterprising are you?’. Furthermore, the questionnaire consisted of 14 questions on key knowledge, behaviours and attributes. Survey results were shown on-screen live and were used to inform the discussion. Some of the findings from this survey suggest more support for ESRs with identifying and pursuing potential funding; managing risks in research and protecting IPR where applicable; self-managing; managing projects and time; communication of research to a variety of audiences; building relationships in academia and other contexts. Strengths are the ability to formulate research questions, collaborative working, enthusiasm, perseverance, and motivation.

Feedback suggested that ESRs found this exercise very helpful.

Two facilitators from USFD were present: Karim Hadjri (Figure 19) and Krzysztof Nawratek (Figure 20).

Figures 19, 20. TS2 Course. Presentation by Karim Hadjri and Krzysztof Nawratek

Case study library

Leandro Madrazo explained the structure of the case studies, and the templates to be used. Afterward, each ESR gave a short presentation of the case study they are working on (Figure 21). Alongside the presentations, Leandro drew attention to some key issues (relationship of the cases with the research projects, use of reliable sources, target groups, copyright of images, videos, and interviews as content) which helped participants to understand the purpose and scope of the case study library to be created in RE-DWELL. ESRs were invited to continue with the documentation of the case studies and to publish them before the next event in Valencia.

Figure 21. ESRs presentations of the case studies.

Network communication processes

Leandro Madrazo and Alexandra Paio provided an overview of the work being done to communicate the activities of the network: social media, web, newsletters, and publications. The template for the coming newsletter 2 was presented, and the protocols for network members to provide content were explained. A tool to introduce publications in the website back office was presented. This will be the communication channel for ESRs to inform about the publications submitted and published. A protocol has started to be developed by ISCTE with the collaboration of two ESRS, Carolina Martín and Androniki Pappa.

Meeting ESRs and management board

In this joint session of ESRs and supervisors, the ESRs expressed their views on the development of the network, communication protocols, and workload. Furthermore, they gave their suggestions for the preparation of the upcoming events, the International Social Housing Festival in Helsinki and the summer school in Valencia.

Game session

In this session, coordinated by Andrea Marikovszky and Annamária Babos from the CoHousing Budapest Association, participants played the game “From a group to a cohousing community” (Figure 22). The trainers used works of fine art that allowed the immersion of the participants. It helped to move away from one's basic state, achieving a focused, problem-oriented approach.

The game had the following phases:

- Team-building, skills development, and support in creating an operating model. The goal was to create a common vision related to the difficulties of community building.
- Negotiations and decisions (representation, participation, responsibility, hierarchy). The aim was to learn methods and forms of democratic decision-making, the practice of sociocracy, and direct democracy.
- Conflict situations (Management protocol, conflict interpretation, and solution search). The goal was to establish a common standard for conflict management.
- Communication. The aim was to formulate rules for internal and external communication.

Building on experiential pedagogical knowledge, the tasks performed in interactive groups of 4-6 people provided an opportunity to experience different forms of collaboration. These also modelled the diverse scale and quality of life resulting from a cohousing living arrangement.

Figure 22. Game session

2.2. Evaluation

The workshop was evaluated by all the participants (in-person and online), through an anonymous online survey. The main goal of the survey was to evaluate their experience and to detect any elements that could be improved in future workshops and summer schools.

The online survey was answered by 9 ESRs and 5 supervisors/co-supervisors, resulting in a response rate of 50%.

Participants were asked to express their opinion on the following aspects of the Budapest workshop (see Table 2). In the first part of the survey questions, participants were asked to rate various aspects of the workshop. In the second part, they had to identify what they particularly liked and what could have been done better. At the end of the survey, they could add comments and recommendations for future network activities.

Table 2. Budapest Workshop: online evaluation

Questions	Answers	Supervisors/Co-supervisors	ESRs	Average
How would you rate the organization of the workshop? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	5	4,11	4,42
Please evaluate the "Guided tour" (from 1 lowest to 5-highest)	8	4	4,28	4,25
Please evaluate "Presentation of ESRs research projects" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4,8	3,55	4
Please evaluate "Roundtable" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	14	4	3,66	3,78
Please evaluate "Documentary and discussion" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4,5	4,5	4,5
Please evaluate "RMT2 course" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	4,5	4,11	4,23
Please evaluate "Vocabulary" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	4,75	3,88	4,15
Please evaluate "Case study Budapest" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	5	4,33	4,53
Please evaluate "Site visit to the case study area" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	13	4,75	4,66	4,69
Please evaluate "TS2 Course" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	11	4,5	4	4,09
Please evaluate "ESR research plan diagrams exhibition" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4	3	3,25
Please evaluate "Case study library" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4,66	3,33	3,66
Please evaluate "Network communication processes" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	11	5	3,66	3,90
Please evaluate "Meeting ESRs and management board" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	12	4,66	4,11	4,25
Please evaluate "Game time" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)	11	5	4,33	4,45

All ESRs who answered the questionnaire and participated rated the **Guided Tour** positively:

“Interesting explanation of the history of social housing in Budapest and the impact of privatization on locals.”

“The tour guide was knowledgeable and gave us a good overview of the specificities and generalities of the housing issues of the district and Budapest.”

However, some ESR mentioned that:

“Good introduction and interesting, just thought it may be useful for the next events to have small “reading list” to familiarize ourselves with the local specificities. That way it may be easier to make sense of what we hear during the field visits”.

Only 55% of the ESRs responded positively to the question on the **Presentation of ESRs’ research projects session**:

“Very useful exercise to follow up on everyone’s research. Great to use Miro to track common features. Nice that it was at the beginning of the session.”

“It was good to see the progress of each ESR project to extract the connections between us”

“Great efforts from the ESRs and organizer (although I’d concern about shrinking the time. Actually, it’s a good thing allowing us only to capture a clear review of the project)”

Some ESRs mentioned:

“Presentations should be more flexible, with ESRs presenting works in progress, the data they are looking at, their questions and problems. Right now presentations are a bit stifling and just depict research projects not actual activities.”

“(…) I am not sure the work with post-its and posters was worth it that much. I think it may have been better to just have feedback sessions, and time to discuss after our presentations.”

“I was quite stressful to cut presentations down from 10 minutes to 5 minutes with such short notice. (…)”

The **Roundtable session** was positively rated by 77% of the ESRs:

“The best round table I attended in all REDWELL activities. The interviewees’ experience was very relevant to most of our topics and I liked their honesty”

“Interesting and knowledgeable presenters”

“Very informative. Good complementary and comparative perspective about what happens in different countries in Europe. (…) As expected, the roundtable is one of the highlights of the RE-DWELL events.”

Nevertheless, some ESRs mentioned that although the session was interesting and useful it was also too long.

“The content is useful and linked to our research, but 3 continuous hours could be too long.”

“The topics discussed were interesting, but the session was very long.”

“The moderator did his best but the guests seemed to be winging it, they looked unprepared, also the lack any readings or prior explanations about the guests works made it difficult to follow.”

“(…) Maybe a different room setting would allow for easier follow-up questions in cases of not very targeted first responses”

The **Documentary and discussion session** received only positive feedback.

“I believe this is the first time we have used this educational tool. It was very effective and helpful; the discussion after the documentary helped me realise other issues that 'could' be important to my work.”

“Eye opener on the risk of middle class to be poor. (…)”

“A very moving and informative piece. It was a very good addition to the programme.”

However, some ESRs mentioned that:

“(…) I think a follow-up task would have been good, especially as it was the end of the day and quite a heavy topic to end with. It could have even been a precursor to a roundtable with academics who work in homelessness and activism or something.”

“(…) However, it felt slightly too intense and maybe long for the specific timeslot. It was that strong that it felt uncomfortable to ask any genuine questions that came in mind while watching it.”

All the ESRs rated the **RMT2 course session** positively, and comments relate primarily to the usefulness of the course.

“Openness to suggestions was great, big hopes about this course.”

“Interesting lecture complemented by relevant literature and discussions that support the development of international comparative research strategies. A very relevant issue in our research network.”

“Not only was the knowledge discussed and presented. But the fact, the timing of the session was perfect since we had just started to formulate our methodology and discover the different theories and possible structures of our research methods. Also the light hands-on activity but very effective.”

Only one respondent mentioned the need for more time:

“Interesting structure, but more time for discussion would be good next time.”

The **Vocabulary session** is rated positively by 66% of the ESRs. Though session comments vary.

“It was really good and more useful to discuss in small groups”

“I really like the way in which the session was addressed. Instead of giving another presentation of a peer review, we had the chance to discuss with our colleagues and give and get more insights about our writing in a more informal but informative fashion.”

“(…) I genuinely appreciate shifting the work to groups, and it was helpful and more efficient.”

Some ESRs made the following comments and suggestions:

“(…) Unnecessary preparation of presentations - it could have been omitted.”

“(…) I wish we had some guidelines (peer-review is not proofreading (as editorial manager), which most of us are confused between these two things). I think peer review is not the best place to act according to common sense. (…)”

“Not sure it was that useful to have a whole session dedicated to this. I think this could have been done remotely, to reduce to the load in Budapest.”

“(…) please let us know beforehand, then we would have changed the way we present the vocabulary.”

All ESRs responded positively to the **Case study Budapest session**. Overall, the session was informative and interesting, as evidenced by some comments:

“Interesting talk and visit. Again, I think these moments really make our events worth it. Getting new perspectives on our topic, getting to know a different context and moments to exchange with locals and among us.”

“The network partners that were invited to present the topic had a comprehensive knowledge of the housing issues in the country. It was quite revealing and very well complemented with the visit later on.”

The **Site visit to the case study area session** was also a success. These comments exemplified the general view:

“Very well delivered. The tour guide was very passionate about the topic, transmitting the message successfully. The case study is an interesting example of municipality involvement in community participation that definitely had to be presented in the workshop.”

“Well organised, and it covers several aspects from the social to community and maybe the local values that I appreciated seeing.”

“Excellent”

The **TS2 Course session** only received positive feedback.

“Interesting topic. Entrepreneurship in the social sector has been getting momentum and is something that we should acknowledge. I am very interested to learn more about it.”

“Easy to digest and pave the way to think beyond the 3 years of RE-DWELL.”

“Getting both views of entrepreneurship, a critical and an “encouraging” perspective was well rounded. Overall, great that this course is geared toward producing a career plan, which may be useful.”

Nonetheless, some ESRs mentioned the need for more time and the inappropriateness of hybrid sessions for debate.

“(…) maybe an extra 10-15 minutes of discussion on the paper would’ve been good.”

“Unfortunately the online participants could only listen to the people on the podium. Hence, most of the discussions were missed.”

Response to the **ESR research plan diagrams exhibition session** was mixed. Some ESRs rated the session positively:

“I find it interesting. It allows us to see in a snapshot how our colleagues are doing with their research. Being able to communicate our investigation in a graphic representation is a skill that we should improve on as researchers. I think it could be good if we could have a session about communicating research graphically, thinking of some of our colleagues that are struggling with this.”

There were some negative comments about the proposed voting procedure. Comments and feedback session on the posters would be appreciated.

“It has been generally agreed that we would benefit from a feedback session, rather than competing / voting for one another “

“Competition regarding posters is not necessary (…)”

“I believe in this type of educational tool, maybe receiving feedback (in a structured way) would be a great addition.”

Some other ESRs mentioned that:

“I think diagrams are nice, but maybe it would make more sense to have a more condensed session with ESR projects and diagram all at the same time?”

“The idea of the one diagram doesn't fit with my research project.”

The ESR's opinion on the **Case study library session** was interesting, useful and important.

“The idea of presenting case studies was very useful. (...)”

“Receiving inputs from 15 cases in less than two hours was impressive all of the cases were 'good', and it helped me to link to other issues and practices.”

However, most of the ESRs mentioned the time constraints.

“(...) in terms of organisation it might have been more valuable to devote some more time in this session so that we have a short Q&A session.”

“Too short for this session, the case studies are important in our network output but now we did not have time to discuss the presentations”

“The time constraints made it a bit challenging and not very productive.”

Some ESRs mentioned that:

“The case study library is taking form and I think we are getting a better idea of how we should shape it. Maybe we could have some of these talks online though? I think a small meeting a couple of weeks before the event may have helped clear some of the questions.”

“It'd be great to know what falls within the remit of a valid case study. If ESRs are not allowed to define it ourselves, we should at least be giving clear indications. Either clear rules on case selection and study, or just accept that case studies will look very different.”

The **Network communication processes** session was positively rated by all ESRs. These comments exemplify the general view:

“This session was needed, a lot of effort was put into it, and it helps to understand the structure of RE-DWELL”

“Very necessary to keep improving the impact that we aim to generate in other audiences and society”

“Great to know that there's the will to listen to us.”

“Very informative”

Some ESRs mentioned that:

“(...) too much detail (LinkedIn button on website is not of greatest urgency).”

“(...) online participants could only listen to the person on the podium.”

The ESRs responded positively to the Meeting ESRs and management board session.

“Great to have time to discuss important issues regarding collaborative efforts.”

“A very necessary discussion that allows us to better understand all the effort, hard work and commitment that is in the backdrop of the project. It is also an opportunity to express concerns, distribute responsibilities and foresee milestones.”

However, some ESRs mentioned the time constraint and the disadvantage of the hybrid session for debate.

“I think these moments are important for us to discuss even though they can be tense, but we could take more time not to rush it.”

“I wish we had more time for this session, and maybe in the following events, a shared document (maybe two weeks before the activity) was sent to ESRs to fill their concerns and discuss them in a structured way or ESRs representative to present the overall concerns.”

“(…) online participants could only listen to the person on the podium.”

87% of the ESRs (who attended) answered positively to the **Game time session**. These comments exemplify the general view:

“The best part of the whole workshop. I have never attended a similar activity before.”

“Excellent! I think this game should have included the supervisors and would have been better as a first activity - like an ice-breaker”

“Effective, engaging and surprisingly insightful to understand the interaction between communities and housing structure.”

One ESR mentioned that:

“Nice to have such an entertaining last session, but we finished the session after 20:30, which is a little late.”

Some other comments or suggestions for upcoming networking activities include a less tight schedule, more time to process the presentations, and additional time for further discussion in each session, lecture series with experts and professionals, innovative involvement of the participants in a playful, informal way of learning like the Game Time Session.

3. Conclusion

The Budapest workshop took place four months after the summer school in Nicosia. The work carried out at the Budapest workshop represented a step forward for network members to gain an understanding of the challenges of affordable and sustainable housing in Europe. The workshop helped to foster knowledge exchange between ESRs, supervisors, and non-academic organizations on the challenges and opportunities of “Community participation in affordable and sustainable housing”. In particular, it contributed to raising the awareness about lack of housing for vulnerable groups, and to strengthening the links between the young researchers. In sum, the experience gained in this workshop also contributed to creating a collaborative and transdisciplinary research environment in which early-stage researchers (ESRs) can develop their projects in connection with each other.

Annex 1 – Posters of ESRs

Industrialising Affordable and Social Housing to meet Circular Goals
 A cradle-to-cradle assessment in combination with Design for Disassembly and Open Building

Supervisor: Dr. Leandro Madroño
Co-supervisors: Dr. Ignacia Guàrdia & Dr. Alexandra Palo

ESR1: Annette Davis
 School of Architecture La Sapienza, Ramon Llull University

Introduction

The climate and housing crises are putting increasing pressure on the construction industry to shift from the current paradigm to a more sustainable and affordable one. Construction accounts for nearly 40% of global energy-related CO2 emissions, while a third of all waste in the EU is generated by construction and demolition. The linear “take-make-waste” model that has industrialised development must shift to a circular approach, which decouples growth from the consumption of finite resources.

Industrialised Construction (IC) or Modular Methods of Construction (MMC) is a broad term encompassing the systematic and controlled production of buildings. IC can be combined with concepts of waste to provide social and affordable housing, such as, and Circular Economy (CE) principles consider the building as a product rather than a one-off prototype and can improve the environmental sustainability of housing while improving affordability, creating profit from waste. This can be achieved through Design for Disassembly (DfD) where detachable standardised elements are easily adapted, reused, repaired, recycled or salvaged.

Project overview

Industrialising housing

Design for Disassembly (DfD)

The concept for IC is that the building is a factory product, that is to say made up of multiple modular products. Production can take place in factories, either off-site or temporarily in on-site halls. It is proposed that a significant proportion of housing in the coming decades across Europe will be built in such factories, and sustainable houses will be made out of standardised elements or “kit of parts” that are designed for disassembly.

Building elements: A kit of parts

The problem

Assessing the sustainability of modular building housing

Sustainability can be holistically measured across all building stages using a cradle-to-cradle Whole Building Life Cycle Analysis (WBLCA) & Whole Building Life Cycle Assessment (WBLCA) & Whole Building Life Cycle Assessment (WBLCAs). The current LCA standard assumes a 60-year life span for the entire building. This does not support the comparison of large elements needed for more modularised housing as take into account varying lifespans of building layers.

Whole Building LCA

The solution

Kit of parts EPDs & Whole Building LCA

A Whole Building EPD would enable the comparison of entire houses from a range of housing types. This would comprise of aggregated EPDs – based on cradle-to-cradle LCAs – for large standard products from a kit of parts library. This makes the comparison of different configurations of parts possible. The aggregated EPD will use an Open Building approach with different lifespans for each layer. This will be used with both industry and research projects.

Whole Building EPD

Key Concepts

1 Industrialised Construction (IC)

Research will be building what is meant by IC in the project context and the life cycle of construction methods. The goal is to understand how it can be pursued through a project level. The goal for the level Design for Disassembly (DfD) alongside other techniques: the project developments.

2 Building Information Modelling (BIM)

It is a knowledge management ICT tool that will support building and project information for a common infrastructure for all building phases and stages. This should be both open standards and a data structure plan, which can be integrated into EPDs and parts. BIM tools are used to create a WBLCA.

3 Open Building (OB)

The proposed OB based building method will have building systems and different standardised layers for each layer, such as: OB for the facade and OB for the structure. This allows a lot of the layers will be used to improve the OB building method.

4 Cradle-to-cradle (C2C) Sustainability Assessment

EPDs will be used to create a comparison from the cradle-to-cradle assessment. This will be used to create a WBLCA and LCA and the future will be used to create a WBLCA and LCA. The use of this data will be used to create a WBLCA and LCA and the future will be used to create a WBLCA and LCA.

Upgrading European social housing to meet the socio-economic needs of today's dwellers, and the environmental needs of the planet: A framework beyond retrofit.

ESR2: Saskia Furman

Supervisor: Leandro Madrazo

Host University: School of Architecture La Salle, Ramon Llull University

**Housing governance beyond city boundaries:
local housing regimes as catalysts for affordability?**
ESR3: Christophe Verrier
Université Grenoble-Alpes

Supervisor:
Paulette Duarte
Co-supervisors:
Adriana Diaconu, Joris Hoekstra

The integration of households' health and wellbeing into LCCA framework

ESR4: Aya Elghandour
 The University of Sheffield

Supervisor:
 Professor Sarah Haddrill

Co-supervisors:
 Dr. Krzysztof Nawrot, Dr. Meera West

Environmental Sustainability of Future Social Housing

ESRS: Mahmoud Alsaeed
Host University: Sheffield University

Supervisor:
Prof. Karm Hagdi

Co-supervisors:
Dr Krzysztof Nawrotek, Dr Ignacio Guillen

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101019722

Comparative analysis of social housing policies' modernization impacts in selected post-socialist countries

ESR6: Marko Horvat
Institute for Social Policy, Faculty of Law, University of Zagreb, Croatia

Supervisor:
Prof. dr. sc. Gajka Božman

Co-supervisors:
Dr. Ing. Gerrit van Bode! Prof. dr. sc. Ivan Ramić

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101019722

Housing Crises In Europe
The new housing precariat in Hungary and Denmark

ESR7: Anna Martin

Centre for Social Sciences, Institute for Sociology

Supervisor:
László Nagyné

Consultation:
Adriana Diaconu, Gerard van Boven

Housing as Social Infrastructure: Urban Living Labs for Planning Experimentation at the Neighbourhood Level

ESRS: Andreas Panagidis
University of Cyprus

Supervisor:
Natalia Charalambous

Co-supervisor:
Andreas Savvides
Tatjana Cormanik

From creator to enabler

The underpinnings and implications of the coDesign.build studio

ESRS Effretyni Bolsooi
University of Cyprus

Supervisor:
Nadia Charambous
Co-supervisors:
Carla Bertoni, Andreas Savvides

Co-creating housing: addressing affordable and sustainable housing in the countries of the European south

ESR10: Zoe Tziika
School of Architecture
Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain

Supervisor:
Carla Soriano
Co-supervisor:
Anna Martínez
Adriana Cizmarty

Research questions	Main research question	How the challenges of affordable and sustainable housing can be addressed in the countries of the European south through practices of co-creation?
	Secondary research questions	What concepts of co-creation practices, what is the relation with cooperative housing or other forms of participation in housing, and why are they important?
	Sub-questions in relation to each location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How does co-creation appear in the framework of affordable and sustainable housing? (social factors, what kinds of processes) What are the objectives for existing processes of co-creation in housing development? In the case of Barcelona, what social institutions and urban policies support these practices emerged, what other models are they addressing? Understand and identify what affordability means and how it can be evaluated in the context of the European social conditions Understand and describe the models for sustainability: What ESRs and how to evaluate it? Are current-related co-creation processes, are the social opportunities? Can we identify the best practices for the provision of affordable and sustainable housing through co-creation practices? Can we identify the strategies and guidelines that have emerged around the emerging practices of housing co-creation? Can we identify a framework for existing processes of co-creation in housing practices?

Research objectives	1. Identify the social conditions	1.1. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.2. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.3. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.4. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.5. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.6. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.7. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south	1.8. Identify the social conditions in the countries of the European south
	2. Framework	2.1. Framework	2.2. Framework	2.3. Framework	2.4. Framework	2.5. Framework	2.6. Framework	2.7. Framework	2.8. Framework
	3. Housing co-creation	3.1. Housing co-creation	3.2. Housing co-creation	3.3. Housing co-creation	3.4. Housing co-creation	3.5. Housing co-creation	3.6. Housing co-creation	3.7. Housing co-creation	3.8. Housing co-creation
	4. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.1. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.2. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.3. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.4. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.5. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.6. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.7. Sustainability in housing co-creation	4.8. Sustainability in housing co-creation
	5. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.1. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.2. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.3. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.4. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.5. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.6. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.7. Affordability in housing co-creation	5.8. Affordability in housing co-creation
	6. Affordability	6.1. Affordability	6.2. Affordability	6.3. Affordability	6.4. Affordability	6.5. Affordability	6.6. Affordability	6.7. Affordability	6.8. Affordability
	7. Case study analysis	7.1. Case study analysis	7.2. Case study analysis	7.3. Case study analysis	7.4. Case study analysis	7.5. Case study analysis	7.6. Case study analysis	7.7. Case study analysis	7.8. Case study analysis
	8. Conclusions & recommendations	8.1. Conclusions & recommendations	8.2. Conclusions & recommendations	8.3. Conclusions & recommendations	8.4. Conclusions & recommendations	8.5. Conclusions & recommendations	8.6. Conclusions & recommendations	8.7. Conclusions & recommendations	8.8. Conclusions & recommendations

The Governance of a Just Housing Transition: Targeting Energy Poverty within the 'Renovation Wave'

Supervisor:
Mara Elenga

Co-supervisors:
Joris Hoekstra
Adrienne Caszary

ESR 11: Tijn Croon
TU Delft

Research Description

The energy transition is likely to involve significant price fluctuations of domestic energy services. Price peaks will put pressure on household expenses and could deepen energy poverty, particularly among low-income households living in inefficient dwellings.

This research project explores what a Just Housing Transition constitutes and seeks to demonstrate how governments and housing associations could adopt, customise, or better target policies, vis-a-vis to have a better understanding of the distribution of energy poverty.

The proposed scientific output is as follows:

- I. Mind the Gap: The Use of Poverty Gap Indicators to Quantify Energy Poverty in the Netherlands
- II. Proposing Energy Poverty Alleviation Policies with Housing Association Professionals
- III. A Comparison between Energy Poverty Policies in France, the UK and the Netherlands
- IV. Tweaking the European Just Housing Transition

Quantifying the Energy Poverty Gap (Art. I)

- This paper compares the implications of the use of different poverty gap indices within the context of energy poverty.
- First, we adopt two conventional income poverty gap indices (Mills Index and Foster-Greer-Thorbecke Index) to measure energy poverty gaps in the Netherlands.
- We then analyse the resulting distributions across three dimensions: spatial, socio-demographic and housing-related.
- Finally, we discuss the policy consequences of energy poverty gap indices, exploring the benefits and potential problems that public entities need to consider before allocating funds based on their modelled outcomes.

Targeting of Housing Associations (Art. II)

- This study intends to combat the mismatch between research and practice, by proactively engaging with various housing association professionals across Europe to find out how qualitative and quantitative knowledge on energy poverty can inform retrofit strategies in different policy contexts.
- It examines the key role that housing associations, with a significant share of their predominantly low-income tenants at risk of energy poverty, have in the Just Transition. Furthermore, it explores whether and how their apparent techno-economic approach to retrofit provision could be altered.

- The aim is to contribute to 'policy transfer' in the broadest sense: foster understanding of practical and regulatory innovations within academia, between research and practice and among housing associations.

Energy Poverty Policies (Art. III)

Just Housing Transition (Art. IV)

Comparative Analysis of Affordable and Sustainable Housing Policies in Europe

ESR12: Alex Fernandez

Supervisor: Marja Elsinga, Marietta Haffner and Gojko Bezovan

Host University: TU Delft

This project's main research goal is to identify and compare policies for the affordable retrofit of Europe's built environment. The analytical framework draws from **various disciplines including economics, public policy, and complexity science**. These disciplines provide the foundations to four research streams:

1. **Analysing of user costs and cash-flows** implications for various housing retrofit policies within the Dutch national context.
2. **Formulating a quantitative model of the housing market**. This second research stream will ponder different modelling techniques that can be applied to the built environment: stock models, agent-based models, structural equation models.
3. **Building on the two prior research objectives**, the preceding model shall be adapted to account for particularities across countries and/or urban areas.
4. **Investigating split incentives in social housing**. This mainly qualitative paper will critically analyse institutional and financial arrangements that foster energy efficiency transitions across different European countries.

These four research streams are empirically and methodologically led aiming to produce actionable insight. However, this project also aspires to **contribute to the theoretical underpinning of public policy analysis**, housing economics and critical social sciences.

First Year Activities

	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEPT	OCT	NOV	DEC	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUNE
DELFT REQUIREMENTS													
PhD Agreement			Done								PHD Report	GCV	
Data management plan									Done	Writing		NOGOT	
Publications & Conferences													
SB22 Conference - 1 st													
Paper – CF/UCCOH													
EEC Conference - Manchester												Poster and research Work	Poster Pres.
RE-DWELL													
Activities		kick-off		Edison		Mosca					Budapest		
• TS	(3)			Pres	Essay								(2)
• RMT	(3)			Conce pt		Essay							(2)
Secondments													Article Zagreb
MSC COURSES TU Delft // BSA													
					Intro Data Science	Agent Based Modelling							
MSC Economics					Econometrics								FINAL EXAM
												Monetary Economics	

Urban commons for Sustainable Local Development in priority urban neighborhoods

ESR13: Androniki Pappa
ISCTE - Instituto Universitário de Lisboa

Supervisor:
Dr. Alessandra Pado
Co-supervisors:
Dr. Carla Semerari, Dr. Paulente Duarte

A framework to implement mass customisation in industrial construction companies to deliver affordable and sustainable housing

ESR14: Carolina Martín Peñuela
ISCTE Lisbon

Supervisor:
Alexandra Paço

Co-supervisor:
Carla Senari, Maria Martí

European Commission

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956062

Annex 2 – Table of interrelationships between ESR projects

	ESR1	ESR2	ESR3	ESR4	ESR5	ESR6
ESR1 Assess		Framework (based on case studies) - Both including a hybrid and standalone. I will also be utilizing energy efficiency across the LCA. I will also be using building case studies.				
ESR2 Saves	Case Study Methodology Utilizing an energy efficiency through quantitative evaluation although I may have also included a case study (DC savings)			Wellbeing and social indicators Don't project existing at these improvements as a general for future research from research.		
ESR3 Connects		Differences between social and affordable housing.		Case studies		
ESR4 Says	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building performance measurement Don't mix design related to evaluate building components Produce Buildings BM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Productivity, health and wellbeing as an important part in the decision making 				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Address high housing efficiency Efficient urban development ESR5 Housing Policy (see the page) ESR6 Housing during state (see house text)

Annex 3 – Concept maps with the vocabulary terms

